

Reliability-Aware Task Allocation Latency Optimization in Edge Computing

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Abstract—Nowadays notable computing is shifted away from the cloud and performed onto the Internet of Things (IoT) devices. This necessity emerges due to the growing needs not only for real-time decision support but also for real-time data processing. When used in critical applications such as search and rescue missions or monitoring and control of critical infrastructure, the overall reliable operation of the application running on these devices becomes a major challenge, especially as system reliability is an application - and h/w - dependent measure. Moreover, performance and energy are typically constrained and vary depending on where the computation takes place, as well as, on the communication channels between the devices. Hence, the problem of task allocation under reliability-performance-energy constraints becomes even more complex in such cloud/hub/edge computing paradigms. In this work, we use a mathematical programming based framework to derive an optimal task allocation based on multiple operational constraints (latency and energy in both computation and communication), while taking into consideration the reliability demands of the application. We consider an architecture consisting of an edge node, an intermediate node (hub), and the cloud infrastructure, and evaluate our approach using a real-life use-case where the proposed framework minimizes the overall latency of the application while considering the reliability demands of each executed task.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, more and more computation is pushed towards the edge, onto the IoT embedded devices, which are now integrated within the computing infrastructure, yielding the cloud/hub/edge paradigm. By offloading tasks from the cloud to the edge [1], [2], we reduce network traffic and enable real-time data processing/analytics. However, as CMOS technology keeps shrinking and devices are operating with near-threshold voltages, the reliability of embedded hardware systems is compromised due to various dependability threats caused by aging-related failures, as well as, environmental conditions such as soft-errors [3], [4]. Therefore, as we move away from the cloud and towards the edge, the devices become error-prone and the reliability of the system begins to degrade [5]. In scenarios such as critical infrastructure monitoring and search-and-rescue operations, building a dependable system

is essential. Designers are required to integrate reliability-aware design methodologies within the system's development cycle, including among others, various types of redundancy. The allocation of an application's tasks in the cloud/hub/edge paradigm, an already challenging process, needs therefore to consider reliability in addition to performance and energy constraints, to increase the system's dependability.

In this paper, we built on top of the recently proposed mathematical programming-based optimization framework of [6], which is able to deliver an optimal task allocation among one edge node, one hub node, and the cloud infrastructure, in such way that the performance of the system is maximized. The contribution of this work focuses on the integration of reliability-aware design techniques such as Dual Modular Redundancy (DMR) into the optimization framework. Furthermore, our framework enables the designer to define the desired reliability levels (user-defined threshold) and decide which tasks are to be executed using DMR, based on each task's precomputed vulnerability factor, such that the overall performance of the application is optimized. In this manner, our framework integrates the DMR mechanism through re-execution (using time-redundancy), which is capable of allocating the redundant task on any computational unit along the computing paradigm. In other words, a task can be executed twice, on the same or different unit (cloud, hub, edge). In addition, it takes into consideration various operational and resource constraints, such as computation latency, energy consumption, memory footprint, as well as, the communication latency and energy consumption, and derives an optimal task allocation with respect to the system's overall performance.

In particular, our framework activates the DMR mechanism, in cases where a specific task executed on a specific computational unit has a vulnerability factor higher than a designer-defined tolerable threshold. To evaluate our framework we use a real-world critical infrastructure monitoring use-case scenario that involves an autonomous UAV-based power transmission lines inspection, suited for the cloud/hub/edge computing paradigm. The allocation results show that our framework manages to optimize the performance of the system under various architectural configurations and constraints for our targeted use-case while enhancing the variability of the results by employing different redundancy threshold levels.

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Fig. 1: Transformation of a task flow graph to the extended task flow graph with selective DMR options: (a) a simple task flow graph with two tasks T_1 and T_2 ; (b) extended task flow graph for the cloud/hub/edge architecture with candidate tasks; (c) extended task flow graph with DMR options incorporated.

The remaining parts of the paper are organized as follows. In Section II, a brief description of our optimization framework is presented. In Section III, the results and the evaluation of the implementation based on a real-life use-case are given, followed by concluding remarks in Section IV.

II. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

We present our approach by the aid of a simple example. Our framework receives as input the extended task flow graph which is derived by the task flow graph of the application. An example of the transformation of the task flow graph [Fig. 1(a)] to the extended versions, is shown in Fig. 1(b)(c). The vertices depicted in the extended task flow graph denote the candidate tasks. The edges of the graph denote the communication edge between a pair of candidate tasks. To form the groups of candidate tasks and to create the extended task flow graph, the application's constraints were taken into account. In addition, through profiling, we calculated several metric values for each candidate task. Each candidate task has six attributes: the computational latency, the energy consumption, the memory footprint, the secondary memory requirements, the generated data and the set of predecessors of the task. For a pair of candidate tasks, the communication edges encapsulate the communication latency and communication energy. It should be noted that in the case where no direct communication between a pair of units exists, e.g. from the edge to cloud and vice versa, an extra communication cost is considered. In that case, communication is achieved through a bridge node. The candidate tasks that use this bridge node are denoted by the *red asterisk* as shown in Fig. 1. It is worth mentioning that the difference between the task flow graph and the extended task flow graph is that in the first one each task will be executed, but in the latter one, only one candidate task per group needs to be executed.

To transform the traditional task flow graph into the extended version, we simply determine whether a task T_i can be allocated to the various computational units. If so, then the T_1 of Fig. 1(a) can be transformed into three candidate tasks T_{1e} ,

T_{1h} , and T_{1c} meaning that T_1 could be executed either on the edge, hub or cloud unit respectively. To incorporate selective DMR, we need the precomputed vulnerability factors for each candidate task, as well as, a designer-defined threshold which is used to determine which tasks should be re-executed. In this work, we assume that the vulnerability factor is given, as it can be derived using a plethora of existing methodologies for extracting application-dependent vulnerabilities [7]. For example, if task T_1 has three candidate tasks as shown in Fig. 1(b), and its candidate task T_{1e} has a vulnerability factor greater than the given threshold, then this candidate task can be transformed into T_{1ee} , T_{1eh} , and T_{1ec} as shown in Fig. 1(c). In other words, the candidate task T_{1eh} indicates that the task T_1 will be executed on the edge and hub nodes. The results from the hub node will be sent back to the edge node where the comparison will take place. It should be noted that the delay of the comparison on each computational unit differs and it is taken into consideration by our framework. By transforming the traditional task flow graph into its extended version, the number of vertices and edges grow linearly with the total number of tasks. This growth is application-dependent and the worst case scenario is shown in Fig. 1, where all tasks, T_1 , T_2 can run on all computational units and their vulnerability factor is bigger than the tolerable threshold (fully extended).

To model the system's energy consumption E we split it into two main parts: the energy needed to execute the allocated tasks, E_x , and the communication energy E_c needed for transmitting and receiving data to and from the computational units, therefore, the system's energy can be described as $E = E_x + E_c$. For the first part, the energy consumption is a simple summation of the power consumption, times the execution time of each allocated candidate task. For the second part, the communication energy consumption is the summation of the total number of bits for transmitting, times the average energy model for one-bit data transmission, and the respective multiplication for the reception.

Due to space limitations, the precise formulation of the optimization problem, which is based on mathematical pro-

gramming, is abstracted at this point. The decision variables correspond to the various computational and communication attributes of the candidate tasks, that is: (i) latency, energy consumption, main and secondary memory usage, as well as, vulnerability factor for each computing device, and (ii) latency and energy consumption of the communication channels between the computing devices. Moreover, the extended task flow graph is further enriched with new candidate tasks for all possible DMR configurations for tasks whose vulnerability factor is above the user-defined threshold. Decision variables are constrained based on the application’s budgets and requirements to optimize (minimize) the overall latency. The proposed framework is capable to detect and report a constraint violation. The reader is referred to [6] for a detailed mathematical description of a simpler version of our formulation, which however does not include the reliability-related constraints and configurations.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION AND RESULTS

A. Case Study: UAV-based power lines inspection

For the evaluation of our framework, we used a real-life problem consisting of fifteen different tasks, involving power lines inspection using an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). The overall process involves the detection of power towers and power lines. In this use case, the UAV is considered as the edge device, the ground control station as the hub node, and a remote server as the cloud infrastructure. The first task of the application involves the image capturing of the power transmission line or the tower. This task can only be performed by the UAV’s camera. Next, the two central parts of this application follow; the power transmission lines detection process, and a convolutional neural network (CNN) based approach [8] for the power tower detection process. The final task is responsible to display the results to the ground operator, therefore, it can only be executed on the ground station. It is worth mentioning, that the tasks of the specific use-case provide enough variability among the different metrics, such as the execution time, the memory footprint, the data generated, the communication latency, therefore, the problem becomes complex enough and the optimal solution in both cases, with and without DMR, cannot be derived by hand.

B. Experimental Setup

We present a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of our framework by using four different computational devices, two high-end and two low-end. A *Raspberry Pi 3* (RPi3) and an *Odroid XU4*, which were considered as low-end and high-end devices respectively, were chosen as the possible edge devices that can be attached as the UAV’s payload to perform the computation. In addition, a *Samsung Tab S2* and a *Mi Notebook Pro*, were chosen as the possible low-end and high-end hub devices respectively. A server equipped with an Intel Xeon E5-2670v2 was used as cloud unit. For our system’s evaluation, four different configurations were employed. Each configuration used a different combination of edge-hub devices, while the cloud unit remained the same

Configuration	Edge Node	Hub Node	Cloud Unit
A	Odroid XU4	Mi Notebook Pro	Server with an Intel Xeon E5-2670v2
B	Odroid XU4	Samsung Tab S2	
C	RPi3	Mi Notebook Pro	
D	RPi3	Samsung Tab S2	

TABLE I: Experimental Setup - Configurations

Communication Channel	Bandwidth (Mbps)
Edge → Hub	30
Hub → Edge	15
Hub → Cloud	40
Cloud → Hub	42

TABLE II: Bandwidth Values of Communication Channels

for all four configurations. These configurations are shown in detail in Table I.

Moreover, we ran our framework in different conditions to reflect for any energy and resource availability variations. To test our framework, we used three different cases for each configuration. For the *first case*, no constraints were applied, hence we considered that all tasks could fit into all computational devices. In other words, it would be possible to run all tasks on a single device if that was necessary. For the *second case*, we assumed that the available resources of main memory at the edge and hub node would be reduced since other tasks-processes would also probably run on these units i.e operating system’s processes. For the third and *final case*, the energy budgets of the edge and hub unit were reduced since other processes not related to our use-case were expected to consume energy. Table II shows the bandwidth of all communication channels.

To obtain the optimal task allocation for each configuration per case, we used the Gurobi Optimizer 8.1 [9] on an Intel® Core i7-4720HQ™ CPU @ 2.6 GHz (Memory: 15.9 GB of RAM). The solution for the specific extended task flow graph was extracted in the order of milliseconds.

C. Results and Discussion

Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4 illustrate the overall latency of the system for each of the four configurations for **three cases** which differ in terms of available energy and memory resources: *all resources are available (case 1)*, *reduced main memory (case 2)* and *reduced energy budgets (case 3)*. More specifically, each graph encapsulates two different metrics, the computation latency (in solid color) for each computational unit *edge*, *hub*, and *cloud* and the communication latency (in patterned color) of each communication channel *edge → hub*, *hub → edge*, *hub → cloud*, and *cloud → hub*. It should be stressed that for each configuration (A, B, C, D) we consider four distinct scenarios. In the first scenario, no redundancy mechanism is applied, while for the second and third scenario a DMR is applied for the top 20% and top 53% of the most critical tasks of the application, respectively. Finally, in the fourth scenario, a DMR mechanism is applied for all tasks. For each scenario, the optimal task allocation is returned by our framework.

In this particular experiment, the results point out that the best performance was provided in the scenario where

Fig. 2: Latency for Case 1: All Resources are Available

no redundancy mechanism was used, while the second-best performance was observed in the scenario where 20% of the most critical tasks have been executed twice using the DMR technique. As expected, for this specific application, the worst performance was observed in the scenario where a DMR scheme was applied for all tasks.

In Figure 2, we observe that there is no significant difference regarding the performance, in terms of latency, amongst the scenarios where a dependability mechanism is activated per each configuration. This happened because the replicants of the specific task were also allocated on the same computational unit, therefore, the only extra cost was the comparison latency and the computation latency needed for the redundant task to be executed in the devices where no parallel execution was available. In Figure 3 and Figure 4, due to the fact that the main memory and energy budgets of both edge and hub devices are reduced, we observe that the task allocation is shifted towards the hub and cloud nodes. In some cases, the replicant task is not allocated on the same unit but it has to shift on a different one. This allocation, has a significant impact on the overall latency, leading to an increased communication latency as observed in both figures where the communication latency was increased by 2 – 4 \times . Furthermore, the similarity of the performances between the different configurations in Figure 3 and Figure 4 exists due to the fact that most of the tasks were allocated on the cloud unit. In our case, the cloud unit had virtually unlimited resources, and was assumed as such in all configurations. However, our framework enables designers to impose limits on the cloud as well.

Moreover, in our use-case, the most reliability demanding tasks were the most demanding, in terms of execution time and resources. It should be noted, that in cases where DMR is used, we assume that the original executed task and the execution of the redundant one return the same results, thus there is no stall for re-executing the task, as this is a run-time parameter.

IV. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this work, we consider the cloud/hub/edge computing paradigm and we examine the problem of allocating optimally an application’s tasks onto the computational units of the system. More specifically, the aim is to minimize the overall latency of the system but at the same time obey the designer-defined reliability demands while taking into consideration the various operational and resource constraints. Our preliminary

Fig. 3: Latency for Case 2: Reduced Memory Resources

Fig. 4: Latency for Case 3: Reduced Energy Budgets

investigation, using DMR as a selective reliability mechanism for critical tasks, allows a designer to early-on identify the impact of selective task re-execution and comparison on application latency while exploring different operating and resource constraints for the edge and hub devices to be utilized.

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